

BUILDING SME PERFORMANCE, HUMAN CAPITAL TRANSFORMATION AND STRATEGIC AGILITY: EMPIRICAL EVIDENCE FROM MADURA ISLAND, INDONESIA

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Abstract

This study aims to examine the role of strategic agility in mediating the relationship of human capital to the performance of batik SMEs in Madura. Batik SMEs in Madura still face many problems, such as, increasingly competitive market competition, lack of human resources, and difficult access to capital which results in the performance of batik SMEs in Madura being weak, while not a few Madurese people depend on their economy from the sale of batik. This research was conducted with quantitative methods, the sample in the study amounted to 133 batik SMEs in Madura. The analysis method uses Structural Equation Modeling (SEM). The results of human capital research contribute to strategic agility, increased skills in product innovation can be the main driver for the productivity of batik SMEs in Madura. However, human capital does not contribute to the performance of batik SMEs in Madura even though having product innovation skills cannot improve the performance of batik SMEs. While strategic agility contributes to the performance of batik SMEs in Madura, the ability to respond to changes quickly can identify new opportunities. While strategic agility is able to mediate the relationship between human capital on the performance of batik SMEs on the island of Madura. Good human resource management will build an instinct that is responsive to opportunities, this is a crucial factor in improving the performance of batik SMEs in Madura, and the contribution of human capital becomes apparent when through strategic agility.

Keywords: Batik Madura, Human Capital, Strategic Agility, SME Performance.

INTRODUCTION

Small and medium enterprises (SMEs) in Indonesia have an important role in national economic growth, and their contribution is very significant to economic growth, including Madura batik SMEs can absorb quite a lot of labor [1]. It is no exaggeration when batik SMEs in Madura are called one of the main pillars in building Madura's economy. Batik SMEs in Madura not only act as economic drivers, creating jobs for people in Madura, but also contribute to the preservation of local cultural wisdom values. Batik in Madura has its own uniqueness, starting from the motif, production process. Despite its contribution, batik SMEs in Madura still face various challenges, such as changes in consumer fashion trends, market competition, lack of human resources, and difficult access to capital which results in the weak performance of batik SMEs in Madura.

Various efforts have been made by the government and Madura batik SMEs to encourage the performance of batik SMEs in Madura, such as increasing online promotion, cyberbranding, road shows to regions, participating in exhibitions. However, these efforts have not had an impact on improving the performance of Madura batik SMEs, thus it is important to immediately conduct an empirical study. [2], and [3], found that to improve the performance of SMEs, human capital is an important factor. This finding is also reinforced by [4], which

discusses the performance of SMEs in Yemen, and recommends measuring SME performance using human capital.

Today, human capital is not only considered as a human resource, but as a strategic investment that has a significant impact on performance. Through skill enhancement and adoption of innovative strategies, human capital can be a driver for improved SME performance [5]. This view is reinforced [5], To have and maintain a competitive advantage, organizations must have and create unique resources. Likewise with [6], found a significant relationship between human capital and SME performance.

Other research results show that organizations that invest in human capital development will increase competitiveness [7]; [8]. This view emphasizes that good human capital management will encourage SMEs to create agility strategies to strengthen SME performance. The theory of strategic agility continues to grow, initially this theory was developed by [9];[10], Highlighting the importance of adaptation, innovation, and decision-making agility in the face of external changes, this theory is an important foundation for organizations to remain competitive. In its development, the concept of strategic agility is increasingly relevant, given changes in consumer behavior triggered by technology.

Although many practitioners and academics understand the importance of strategic agility in organizations, there is no literature that integrates human capital, and strategic agility as a mediator of SME performance, especially in the batik sector SMEs in Madura. Other research on strategic agility was conducted by [11], found strategic agility has a direct impact on business performance. These results are reinforced by [12], found strategic agility to build SMEs' survival instincts. In contrast to [9], in his study found that strategic agility does not have a significant effect on SME performance. Based on the differences in these findings, it becomes a gap and encourages researchers to explore the role of strategic agility in mediating the influence of human capital on the performance of batik SMEs in Madura.

The findings of this study can be an important source for batik SMEs in Madura in improving the performance of batik SMEs, and the government in drafting regulations on batik SMEs, considering that many Madurese people still depend on their economy on the sale of batik. In addition, Madura batik is one of the cultural heritages that must be preserved and has uniqueness. This research also contributes to the literature on the importance of strategic agility in building the performance of batik SMEs on the island of Madura by adding the role of human capital

LITERATURE REVIEW AND HYPOTHESIS DEVELOPMENT

Human Capital and Strategic Agility

Effective human capital is key to increasing the level of strategic agility of organizations in the face of intense competition [13]. Other empirical evidence shows that organizations with strong human capital tend to be more able to adapt quickly to changes in the business environment [14]. Another view suggests that organizations that invest in human capital development will increase their competitiveness [8]. This finding explains the importance of human capital in creating strategic agility through continuous development of employee skills and potential.

Likewise with [5], highlights that quality human capital will improve an organization's ability to adapt to rapid market changes. This means that investment in the development of employee skills and knowledge not only increases individual productivity but also improves the

organization's ability to implement responsive strategies. [15], discusses that human capital is a key asset that supports strategic agility through the development of a culture of innovation and continuous learning. Research shows that human capital plays an important role in strengthening strategic agility.

H1: There is a relationship between human capital and strategic agility

Human Capital and SME Performance

Human capital is the accumulation of competencies, knowledge, and skills needed to perform work that generates economic value for the organization. The formation of added value contributed by human capital in carrying out tasks and work will provide sustainable revenue in the future for the organization [16]. Human capital is part of the analytical instruments at the individual level. Furthermore, working individuals require specialized knowledge and skills as enclosed in human capital theory, which explains that investments in knowledge and skills will be more profitable [17]. Through the enhancement of superior skills and the adoption of innovative strategies, human capital can be a key driver of sustainable productivity gains [3]. This statement underscores the importance of productivity development in organizations by putting a special focus on the potential and contribution of human capital.

Several recent studies have proven the relationship between company performance and HR management processes in companies such as [4], conducted research on the relationship between human capital and company performance, the results showed a positive relationship between human capital and company performance. Begitupun [18], proved a positive and significant relationship between human capital and company performance. Other empirical studies related to the relationship between human capital in the form of knowledge resources and company performance include those conducted by [5], stated that only companies that can produce new knowledge on an ongoing basis are able to achieve a better position to have a competitive advantage. Furthermore [19], shows that human capital has a positive and significant influence on the performance of SMEs in Vietnam. Similar results are also expressed in research [3], which found that human capital has a positive and significant effect on the performance of SMEs.

H2: There is a relationship between human capital and SME performance

Strategic Agility as a Mediator

Strategic agility is the organization's ability to anticipate, adapt, and change the business to changes in the external environment, emphasizing the importance of deeply understanding the effects of technological developments and the ability to change business strategies innovatively [20], [11]. Simply put, strategic agility plays an important role in maintaining the market when organizations compete in a volatile business environment. Strategic agility refers to an organization's ability to be flexible in decision-making and have the ability to adapt quickly to changes in the business environment. This opinion is reinforced by [21], There are two main aspects underlying this: flexibility in decision-making and the ability to adapt quickly, as key elements in business strategy.

An organization's ability to quickly and effectively adjust its business strategy in response to market changes is the key to achieving and sustaining performance. This opinion is reinforced by [12], reveals strategic agility played an important role in building the survival instincts of SMEs in Finland during the pandemic. This research shows the importance of strategic agility

in improving business resilience and sustainability. Research by [22], found that high levels of strategic agility can strengthen SME performance by improving operational efficiency, identifying new market opportunities, and responding to competition, which in turn will contribute positively to SME growth and performance.

H3: There is a relationship between strategic agility and SME performance

H4: Strategic agility can mediate human capital on SME performance

RESEARCH METHODS

Human capital is measured through skills, knowledge, abilities, and commitment [5]. While strategic agility is measured by sensing agility, decision-making agility, and acting agility [11]. This study uses a quantitative approach, data collection techniques using a questionnaire with the Likert scale method, namely the choice of five strongly agree, four agree, three neutral, two disagree, and one strongly disagree. Respondents in this study were batik SMEs in Madura Indonesia who were members of the Madura batik peguyuban, the sample used was 133 Madura batik SMEs. The analysis technique uses descriptive statistics. Data is analyzed using Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) with SPSS and SEM AMOS programs. The analysis was carried out through data normality, convergent and discriminant validity, goodness of fit, and hypothesis testing.

Gambar 1 : Research Framework

RESULTS

Respondent Characteristics

Respondents seen from the age of 25-32 years as many as 7 (17%), age 33-44 years as many as 21 respondents (15.8%). Respondents aged 45-56 years were 105 respondents or 78.9%, thus the majority of respondents were aged 45-56 years. male gender 122 (91.7%), 11 respondents (8.3%) female. The highest level of education is junior high school which is 64 respondents (48.1%), high school 44 respondents (33.1%), and elementary school 14 respondents (10.5%), S1 11 respondents (8.3%). Based on the origin of Pamekasan district 75

respondents (56.4%), 24 respondents (18.0%) from bangkalan, and 20 respondents (15.0%) from Sumenep district, 14 respondents (10.5%) from Sampang district

Normality Test

Data normality testing is done by observing the multivariate critical ratio value. If the multivariate critical ratio value is between -2.58 to 2.58, the data distribution can be categorized as normal [23]. The following are the results of multivariate normality testing in the structural equation model:

Table 1: Multivariate Normality Test Results

Variable	Min	max	skew	c.r.	kurtosis	c.r.
Y1.3	9,000	15,000	-,076	-,325	-1,024	-2,182
Y1.2	9,000	15,000	-,377	-1,609	-,728	-1,552
Y1.1	6,000	10,000	-,273	-1,165	-,781	-1,665
Y2.3	9,000	15,000	-,238	-1,013	-,884	-1,883
Y2.2	9,000	15,000	-,259	-1,105	-,582	-1,240
Y2.1	6,000	15,000	-,376	-1,603	-,139	-,296
X1.4	6,000	10,000	-,264	-1,127	-,783	-1,669
X1.3	6,000	10,000	-,236	-1,008	-1,038	-2,212
X1.2	6,000	10,000	-,334	-1,423	-,678	-1,445
X1.1	7,000	10,000	-,628	-2,677	-,744	-1,586
Multivariate					6,549	2,207

The multivariate critical ratio value is 2.207 which is between -2.58 to 2.58, it can be concluded that the assumption of multivariate normality is met which is required by SEM analysis.

Confirmatory Factor Analysis

The measurement results of indicators that can form variables, human capital, and, strategic agility and performance of batik SMEs with Confirmatory Factor Analysis are explained as follows:

Table 2: Exogenous Variable Test Results

Indicator	Latent Variable	Factor Loading	Critical Ratio	P-value	Description
Skills	Human Capital	0,651	Fixed	0,000	Valid
Knowledge	Human Capital	0,847	8,134	0,000	Valid
Ability	Human Capital	0,762	7,239	0,000	Valid
Commitment	Human Capital	0,783	7,530	0,000	Valid
Reliability Construct	= 0,898	(cut-off value = 0,7)			Reliable
Variance Extract	= 0,871	(cut-off value = 0,5)			Reliable

Based on Table 2. The factor loading value of each indicator exceeds the cut-off value of 0.5, the probability value (p) is less than or equal to 0.05, the Construct Reliability value of 0.898 is greater than the cut-off value of 0.7 and the Variance Extract value of 0.871 is greater than the cut-off value of 0.5. The results of this test indicate that the indicators tested have good reliability in forming and operationalizing human capital variables.

Table 3: Test Results of Mediating Variables and Endogenous Variables

Indicator	Latent Variable	Factor Loading	Critical Ratio	P-value	Description
Sensing agility	Strategic Agility	0,749	Fixed	0,000	Valid
Decision-making agility	Strategic Agility	0,904	10,741	0,000	Valid
Acting agility	Strategic Agility	0,749	8,483	0,000	Valid
Advantages	SME performance	0,628	Fixed	0,000	Valid
Sales growth	SME performance	0,787	7,630	0,000	Valid
Market share	SME performance	0,720	6,690	0,000	Valid
Reliability Construct	= 0,807	(cut-off value = 0,7)			Reliable
Variance Extract	= 0,771	(cut-off value = 0,5)			Reliable

In Table 3. Shows the factor loading value of each indicator exceeds the cut-off value of 0.5, the probability value (p) is less than or equal to 0.05, the Construct Reliability value of 0.807 is greater than the cut-off value of 0.7 and the Variance Extract value of 0.771 is greater than the cut-off value of 0.5. The SME performance indicator has a factor loading value of 0.787. This shows that the indicators tested have good reliability in forming and operationalizing the strategic agility latent variable, and the performance of batik SMEs in Madura.

SEM Analysis Results

In accordance with the research objectives, a structural model is developed, the value of this index is compared with the critical value (cut-of value) of each index. A good model is expected to have goodness of fit indices that are greater than or equal to the critical value. The test results with Structural Equation Modeling (SEM), are presented as follows:

Figure 2: Path Diagram of SEM Analysis Results

Table 4: Test Results of Goodness of Fit Modified Structural Model

Goodness Of Fit Index	Cut-off Value	Model Results	Description
Chi-Square	39,252	108,787	Good
Probability <i>Chi-Square</i>	$\geq 0,05$	0,076	Good
CMIN/DF	$\leq 2,00$	0,89	Good
RMSEA	$\leq 0,08$	0,041	Good
GFI	$\geq 0,90$	0,909	Good
AGFI	$\geq 0,90$	0,862	Margin Model
TLI	$\geq 0,95$	0,974	Good
CFI	$\geq 0,95$	0,981	Good

Based on the evaluation results of the Goodness of Fit Index criteria in table 4, it shows that the overall model evaluation has been met, so the model can be accepted.

Hypothesis Testing

Structural Equation Model (SEM) analysis using AMOS 23 to test the hypothesis. The basis for testing the hypothesis is used critical ratio (Cr) from the regression weight output. The research hypothesis will be accepted if the p value < 0.05 or 5% significance, then it can be said that there is a significant influence.

Table 5: Measurement, human capital, strategic agility, SME performance

Relationship			Path Coefficient	S.E	C.R.	p-Value	Description
Human Capital	-->	Strategic Agility	0,844	0,184	6,549	0,000	Significant
Human Capital	-->	SME Performance	0,244	0,308	1,520	0,128	Not Significant
Strategic Agility	-->	SME Performance	0,796	0,255	4,201	0,000	Significant
No	Exogenous Variables	Mediating Variable	Endogenous Variable	Standardized Direct Effect	Standardized Indirect Effect	Standardized Total Effect	Results
1.	X1	Y1	Y2	0,244	0,671	0,915	Full Mediation

The coefficient value of the effect of human capital on strategic agility is 0.844, with a critical ratio value of $6.549 > 2$ and a p-value of 0.000 smaller than 5% statistical significance. This finding shows that human capital has a significant impact on strategic agility, thus, the first hypothesis (H1) is proven and tested. The coefficient value of the effect of human capital on the performance of batik SMEs in Madura is 0.244 and the critical ratio value of 1.520 is smaller than 2, while the probability value of 0.128 is greater than the 5% significance limit. These results indicate the application of human capital has no impact on the performance of batik SMEs in Madura, so the second hypothesis (H2) is not proven. While the coefficient value of the effect of strategic agility on the performance of batik SMEs in Madura is 0.796, with a critical ratio value of $4.201 > 2$, and a probability value of 0.000 smaller than the 5% significance limit. meaning that strategic agility has a significant impact on the performance of batik SMEs in Madura, these results prove the third hypothesis (H3) is proven and tested. The results of the analysis of the role of strategic agility as a mediating influence of human capital on the performance of batik SMEs in Madura have a total effect value of 0.915 greater than the direct effect of 0.244. The results of this study prove that strategic agility has a role as a mediator, and the fourth hypothesis (H4) is accepted and tested.

DISCUSSION

The Effect of Human Capital on Strategic Agility

Human capital has an effect on strategic agility in batik SMEs in Madura. Human capital, which consists of various elements such as skills, abilities, knowledge, and commitment, is a key factor in increasing the strategic agility of batik SMEs in Madura. This product innovation skill can be in the form of developing traditional motifs with a contemporary touch, exploring more environmentally friendly coloring techniques, utilizing local raw materials. This ability to innovate will make it easier for batik SMEs in Madura to adapt to modern consumer preferences, while increasing the competitiveness of the batik industry nationally and internationally.

Strengthening aspects of human capital, such as improving the skills, knowledge, and commitment of human resources will create a strong foundation for innovation in the growth of batik SMEs in Madura. This conception is in accordance with the Resource Based View theory [24], Unique and valuable human resources, such as skills, knowledge, and commitment, can be a source of competitive advantage. This means that batik SMEs in Madura that invest in human capital development will increase the organization's ability to adapt to market changes.

The Effect of Human Capital on SME Performance

Human capital has no effect on the performance of batik SMEs in Madura, although many literatures state such as [5], This study argues that human capital is an important factor in influencing the performance of SMEs, on the other hand human capital can encourage productivity and efficiency.

However, the results of this study found that human capital is not enough to have an impact on the performance of batik SMEs in Madura. One of the causes is the lack of practical implementation of the skills possessed by batik SMEs in Madura.

The role of human capital is not only limited to the mastery of technical batik skills, but includes the development of managerial skills, marketing strategies. In addition, it is important to immediately pay attention to regeneration, regeneration is an important step that must be taken for the sustainability of this creative industry that has economic value. By regenerating, batik SMEs in Madura not only preserve cultural heritage, but make investments that can combine tradition with innovation.

The Effect of Strategic Agility on SME Performance

The results showed that strategic agility has a positive and significant effect on the performance of batik SMEs in Madura. This shows that an increase in the ability of strategic agility of batik SMEs in Madura has the potential to directly improve the performance of batik SMEs in Madura.

This increase in capability includes the ability to respond quickly to change, adapt to market conditions. So that strategic agility becomes a crucial element that determines the competitiveness of batik SMEs in Madura and can identify new opportunities. This finding is consistent with [25], which found to build the ability of the organization to have to make rapid strategic adaptations.

The practical implications of these findings confirm the importance of developing management training programs that focus on increasing the capacity of strategic adaptation for batik SMEs in Madura. Likewise [12], found strategic agility plays an important role in building a survival instinct for SMEs in the face of market changes, and emphasized the importance of strategic agility in improving business performance.

The Effect of Human Capital, on SME Performance Through Strategic Agility

Human capital has an impact on the performance of batik SMEs in Madura through strategic agility. This finding shows that good human resource management will build a responsive instinct to opportunities, and this is a crucial factor in improving the performance of batik SMEs in Madura, which in turn the contribution of human capital becomes apparent when through strategic agility.

The ability of batik SMEs in Madura to adapt and respond to opportunities and changes in the business environment is strongly influenced by strategic agility, the role of strategic agility as a mediator between human capital and the performance of batik SMEs in Madura shows how important a strategic approach is in building innovative skills for batik SMEs in Madura, the development of human capital and strategic agility is a step that cannot be ignored to achieve optimal performance for batik SMEs in Madura.

This finding is consistent with the Resource Based View theory [24] . dan [25], which emphasizes the importance of human resource transformation, and highlights the role of strategic agility as an important factor in improving SME performance, meaning that investment in human resource development, such as opportunity-seeking agility, adapting to the market environment, decision-making agility, and innovation-oriented skill enhancement, can have a significant impact on improving the performance of batik SMEs in Madura.

CONCLUSION

Human capital contributes greatly to the strategic agility of batik SMEs in Madura, increasing skills in innovating products can be a major driver for the productivity of batik SMEs in Madura. However, the results of this study indicate that human capital does not contribute to the performance of batik SMEs in Madura. Although batik SMEs in Madura have the skills of product innovation to be interesting/unique, it cannot improve the performance of batik SMEs in Madura. While strategic agility has a significant impact on the performance of batik SMEs in Madura. The ability to respond to changes quickly shows that batik SMEs in Madura that have strategic agility can identify new opportunities. Human capital has a positive and significant influence on the performance of batik SMEs in Madura through strategic agility as a mediator.

Limitations and Suggestions for Further Research

This study only focuses on batik SMEs in the Madura region, so the results of this study cannot be generalized to other regions with different characteristics, to get a better concept, further research is needed on the same variables and a wider and different type of company. For future research, it is expected to use a qualitative approach, to explore a deeper understanding, explore other mediating and moderating variables, such as innovative culture, market orientation, digitalization, government regulation, and local culture, and add social capital variables to measure SME performance.

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